

**New species and new records of ichneumon wasps,
with descriptions of two new species of *Melalophacharops* Uchida, 1928
(Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae)**

Zoltán Vas

*Hungarian Natural History Museum, Department of Zoology, Hymenoptera Collection,
H-1088 Budapest, Baross utca 13, Hungary. E-mail: vas.zoltan@nhmus.hu*

Abstract – Palaearctic, Oriental, Australasian, Afrotropical and Neotropical species of the subfamilies Campopleginae, Hybrizontinae, Mesochorinae and Ophioninae of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) are treated. Two new species of Campopleginae are described, *Melalophacharops nitens* sp. nov. from Taiwan, and *Melalophacharops chryseus* sp. nov. from Australia, the latter representing the first described species of the genus from the Australasian region. The following new country records are presented: Campopleginae: *Melalophacharops everese* (Uchida, 1957) from Taiwan, *Microcharops tibialis* (Cresson, 1872) from Paraguay, *Lemophagus curtus* Townes, 1965 from Hungary, *Phobocampe confusa* (Thomson, 1887) from North Macedonia, *Rhimphoctona megacephalus* (Gravenhorst, 1829) from Lebanon; Hybrizontinae: *Ghilaromma fuliginosi* (Wilkinson, 1930) from Hungary; Mesochorinae: *Mesochorus laricis* Hartig, 1838 from Hungary; Ophioninae: *Dicamptus pellucidus* (Kriechbaumer, 1894) from Kenya, *Dictyonotus nigrocyaneus* (Tosquinet, 1903) from Eritrea, *Enicospilus cederbergi* Johansson, 2018 from Hungary, *Enicospilus exoticus* (Morley, 1912) from French Guiana, *Enicospilus leucocotis* (Tosquinet, 1896) from Tanzania, *Enicospilus quietus* (Seyrig, 1935) from Tanzania, *Ophion areolaris* Brauns, 1889 from Hungary, *Thyreodon atriventris* (Cresson, 1874) from French Guiana and Nicaragua, and *Thyreodon maculipennis* Cresson, 1874 from Nicaragua.

Key words – taxonomy, species description, distribution, Palaearctic region, Oriental region, Australasian region, Afrotropical region, Neotropical region, Campopleginae, Hybrizontinae, Mesochorinae, Ophioninae

INTRODUCTION

Identification of the Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) material of the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest (HNHM) resulted in two new species and several new faunistic records, which are presented in this paper. Taxonomy and nomenclature follow YU & HORSTMANN (1997) and YU *et al.* (2016). Morphological terminology follows GAULD (1991) and GAULD *et al.* (1997);

however, in cases of wing veins the corresponding terminology of TOWNES (1969) is also used. Identifications were based on the works of ASHMEAD (1905), UCHIDA (1928, 1932, 1957), SONAN (1930), TOWNES (1970), KUSIGEMATI (1967, 1987), KASPARYAN (1976), GAULD & MITCHELL (1978), HORSTMANN (1980, 2004), BROCK (1982), GAULD (1984, 1988), GUPTA (1987), ACHTERBERG (1999), GAULD & JANSEN (2004), SEDIYV (2004), RIEDEL (2018), VARGA (2017), JOHANSSON (2018), VAS *et al.* (2022), and on examination of adequate type materials (at least from photos of scientific quality). The specimens were identified by the author using a Nikon SMZ645 stereoscopic microscope. Label data of type specimens are given verbatim, with additions and explanations in square brackets if necessary.

RESULTS

Taxonomy

Family: Ichneumonidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily: Campopleginae Förster, 1869

Genus: *Melalophacharops* Uchida, 1928

Type species: *Melalophacharops tamanukii* Uchida, 1928, original designation

Diagnosis: head lenticular; apical margin of clypeus impressed, sharp; scutellum convex in profile, lateral carina at most basally discernible; areolet absent; nervellus not intercepted by discoidella; axillus vein present; sub-basal cell of hind wing relatively narrow; hind basitarsus with a distinct midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs, the row appearing like a sharp carina; suture separating first tergite from first sternite situated distinctly below mid-height at basal third of first metasomal segment; glymma small to virtually absent; ovipositor sheath about as long as apical depth of metasoma (diagnosis based on TOWNES (1970), GAULD (1984) and GUPTA (1987)).

Melalophacharops nitens sp. nov.

(Figs 1–2)

Type material – Holotype: female, “Formosa [= Taiwan], Taihorin [= Dalin], XI.1908, [leg. H.] Sauter”; specimen pinned, id. HNHM-HYM 155162. Paratype: female, “Formosa [= Taiwan], Ins. Lambeh [= Liuqiu Island], I.1908, [leg. H.] Sauter”; specimen pinned, id. HNHM-HYM 155163. Holotype and paratype are deposited in the HNHM.

Diagnosis – The new species can be identified among the known species of the genus by the following character states in combination: ocular-ocellar distance $1.2\times$ as long as ocellus diameter; face granulate and weakly rugulose; malar space $0.7\times$ as long as basal width of mandible; scutellum almost evenly convex in profile; mesopleuron punctate-granulate with oblique wrinkles anterior to speculum and below speculum; ventral part of epicnemial carina slightly elevated; lateromedian longitudinal carina of propodeum strong, lateral longitudinal carina obsolescent behind costula, anterior transverse carina complete and strong, posterior transverse carina strong but its median section absent; area superomedia small, pentagonal, slightly longer than wide, its lateral sides right behind costulae subparallel to slightly convergent, posteriorly opened; area petiolaris medially rather distinctly impressed; glymma very small, narrow, barely discernible; scapus and pedicellus yellow, dorsally more or less brownish; tegula brownish yellow; first tergite of metasoma black, second tergite blackish to dark brown, laterally and subapically narrowly orange-brown, third and following tergites dorsally dark brown, laterally orange to orange-brown; fore and middle legs orange, except fore coxa and trochanter yellow and apical tarsomeres brownish; hind coxa black, apically orange-brown, trochanter and trochantellus pale orange, femur orange, tibia orange, basally and apically brownish, tarsus brownish.

Figs 1–2. *Melalophacharops nitens* sp. nov., 1 = habitus, holotype, 2 = propodeum, series of short lines in the midline indicate the distinct impression, not surface sculpture (photo by Zoltán Vas, drawing by Viktória Szőke)

Description – Female (Figs 1–2). Body length ca. 5 mm, fore wing length ca. 3.5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 24–26 flagellomeres; first flagellomere ca. 4× as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres subquadrate to slightly longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, hairs dense and short. Ocular-ocellar distance 1.2× as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli 1.3× as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits weakly indented, about parallel. Gena finely coriaceous, very short, strongly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view 0.35–0.4× as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina distinctly before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons almost flat, transversely rugose on granulate background, median longitudinal carina absent. Face almost flat in profile, granulate and weakly rugulose. Clypeus very weakly separated from face, flat in profile, granulate with rather weak rugulosity and indistinct traces of punctures, small, its apical margin truncate, sharp. Malar space 0.7× as long as basal width of mandible. Mandible wide and short, lower margin with relatively wide flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely but relatively abruptly narrowed before teeth; upper mandibular tooth slightly longer and wider than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma relatively stout, matt, with dense, short hairs. Pronotum with strong, transverse wrinkles on lower half, upper half granulate; epomia strong. Mesoscutum rugulose on granulate surface with weak traces of punctures, slightly shorter than wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide and moderately deep. Scutellum almost evenly convex in profile, rugulose with rather weak punctures, lateral carina discernible only at extreme base. Mesopleuron distinctly punctate on finely granulate surface, with moderately strong, oblique wrinkles anterior to speculum and below speculum; speculum large, smooth or very finely granulate. Epicnemial carina complete, strong, pleural part bent to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it at about its middle height, transversal part (i.e., the part at the level of sternaulus running through the epicnemium to the ventral edge of pronotum) not developed, ventral part (behind fore coxae) slightly elevated. Sternaulus indistinct. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, elevated. Metanotum ca. 0.4× as long as scutellum. Metapleuron with weak traces of punctures, dorsally weakly sculptured, ventrally more or less rugulose-granulate, juxtacoxal carina distinct, long, reaching posterior margin of metapleuron; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle small, circular, separated from pleural carina by 2× its length, connected to pleural carina by a weak ridge. Propodeum short, convex in lateral view, granulate before anterior transverse carina, rugose behind anterior transverse carina, posteriorly with a median impression. Propodeal carinae: lateromedian longitudinal carina strong; lateral longitudinal carina obsolescent behind costula; anterior transverse carina, including costula, complete and strong; posterior transverse carina strong

but its median section absent. Area basalis triangular, about as long as its anterior width, posteriorly more or less merged into a single, short longitudinal carina. Area superomedia small, pentagonal, slightly longer than wide, its lateral sides right behind costulae subparallel to slightly convergent, posteriorly opened. Area petiolaris confluent with area superomedia, medially rather distinctly impressed. Fore wing without areolet, *3rs-m* absent, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) postfurcal, intercubitus (*2rs-m*) as long as to longer than abscissa of *M* between *2rs-m* and *2m-cu*, their angle obtuse; distal abscissa of *Rs* long, straight; nervulus (*cu-a*) postfurcal by about its width, distinctly inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted distinctly above its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell almost right-angled. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) vertical, straight, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus; axillus vein present. Coxae finely granulate with weak punctures. Hind femur ca. 5× as long as high. Inner spur of hind tibia 0.6–0.7× as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Hind basitarsus with a distinct midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs, the row appearing like a sharp carina. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma compressed, shagreened (except first tergite almost smooth) with weak, barely discernible traces of punctures, and with moderately sparse, short hairs. First tergite relatively stout, 2.7–2.9× as long as its apical width, 1.4× as long as second tergite; glymma very small, narrow and shallow, indistinct; dorsomedian carina of first tergite indistinct. First sternite not reaching level of spiracle. Second tergite 1.2× as long as its apical width; thyridium subcircular, relatively large, its distance from basal margin of tergite 0.5–0.6× as long as its length. Posterior margins of apical tergites slightly concave, not excised. Ovipositor sheath slightly longer than apical depth of metasoma; ovipositor strong, weakly upcurved, dorsal subapical notch distinct.

Colour: Flagellum brown, scapus and pedicellus yellow, dorsally more or less brownish. Head black, palpi yellowish, mandible yellow, mandibular teeth brownish. Mesosoma black, tegula brownish yellow. Metasoma: first tergite black; second tergite blackish to dark brown, laterally and subapically narrowly orange-brown; third and following tergites dorsally dark brown, laterally orange to orange-brown. Wings subhyaline, wing veins and pterostigma brown. Fore and middle legs orange, except fore coxa and trochanter yellow and apical tarsomeres brownish. Hind leg: coxa black, apically orange-brown; trochanter and trochantellus pale orange; femur orange; tibia orange, basally and apically brownish; tarsus brownish. Hairs greyish.

Male: Unknown.

Distribution – Taiwan.

Etymology – The specific epithet *nitens* is a Latin one-termination participle treated as an adjective, meaning beautiful, elegant.

Remarks on identification – Among the species of the genus, due to its slightly similar propodeal carination, *Melalophacharops nitens* sp. nov. is most similar to *Melalophacharops balajensis* Kusigemati, 1987, described and known from Nepal (KUSIGEMATI 1987). The latter species can be readily distinguished from the new species by its much shorter ocular-ocellar distance (ca. 0.5× as long as ocellus diameter), shorter malar space (0.5× as long as basal width of mandible), differently shaped area superomedia (its lateral sides strongly convergent behind costulae), not distinctly impressed area petiolaris, and different surface sculpture of propodeum (cf. KUSIGEMATI (1987: fig. 2)), predominantly dark coxae, and much more extensively orange-coloured metasoma (postpetiolus orange, following tergites orange with minor blackish markings).

***Melalophacharops chryseus* sp. nov.**

(Figs 3–4)

Type material – Holotype: male, “Australia, Queensland, Townsville, 1900, leg. Bíró L.”; specimen card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155164. Paratypes: two males, same label data; specimens card-mounted, id. HNHM-HYM 155165, 155166. Holotype and paratypes are deposited in the HNHM.

3

4

Figs 3–4. *Melalophacharops chryseus* sp. nov., 3 = habitus, holotype, 4 = propodeum, surface sculpture not indicated (photo by Zoltán Vas, drawing by Viktória Szőke)

Diagnosis – The new species can be identified among the known species of the genus by the following character states in combination: ocular-ocellar distance $0.6\text{--}0.7\times$ as long as ocellus diameter; face rugose; malar space $0.4\text{--}0.5\times$ as long as basal width of mandible; scutellum almost evenly convex in profile; mesopleuron rugose-punctate with strong, oblique wrinkles anterior to speculum and below speculum; ventral part of epicnemial carina slightly elevated; lateromedian longitudinal carina of propodeum strong except behind costula shortly obsolete, lateral longitudinal carina weak behind costula, anterior transverse carina complete and strong, posterior transverse carina only laterally developed; area superomedia pentagonal, wider than long, its lateral sides behind costulae obsolete, posteriorly opened; glymma very small, barely discernible; scapus and pedicellus bright yellow with a narrow, brown stripe dorsally; tegula bright yellow; metasoma pale orange with a narrow, blackish band on posterior margin of second tergite; fore and middle legs, including coxae, ivory; hind leg, including coxa, pale orange, except tarsus more or less brownish.

Description – Male (Figs 3–4). Body length ca. 6.5 mm, fore wing length ca. 5.5 mm.

Head: Antenna with 41 flagellomeres; first flagellomere ca. $3.5\times$ as long as its apical width; preapical flagellomeres slightly longer than wide. Head transverse, matt, hairs dense and moderately long. Ocular-ocellar distance $0.6\text{--}0.7\times$ as long as ocellus diameter, distance between lateral ocelli $1.3\times$ as long as ocellus diameter. Inner eye orbits strongly indented, about parallel. Gena finely coriaceous, very short, very strongly narrowed behind eyes, in dorsal view $0.3\times$ as long as eye width. Occipital carina complete, reaching hypostomal carina distinctly before base of mandible; hypostomal carina slightly elevated. Frons flat, rugose, median longitudinal carina absent. Face weakly convex in profile, rugose to rugose-punctate. Clypeus very weakly separated from face, almost flat in profile, punctate, small, its apical margin truncate, sharp. Malar space $0.4\text{--}0.5\times$ as long as basal width of mandible. Mandible wide and short, lower margin with relatively wide flange from base towards teeth, flange obliquely narrowed at teeth; upper mandibular tooth slightly longer and wider than lower tooth.

Mesosoma: Mesosoma relatively stout, matt, with rather dense pilosity, hairs long, especially on scutellum and propodeum, except on mesoscutum short. Pronotum with rather strong, transverse wrinkles on lower two-thirds, upper third finely granulate; epomia strong. Mesoscutum densely rugulose-punctate on granulate surface, slightly shorter than wide, convex in profile; notaulus not developed. Scuto-scutellar groove wide and deep. Scutellum almost evenly convex in profile, rugose, lateral carina discernible only at extreme base. Mesopleuron impressed along speculum, strongly rugose-punctate with rather strong, oblique wrinkles anterior to speculum and below speculum; speculum large, polished, smooth. Epicnemial carina complete, strong, pleural part bent

to anterior margin of mesopleuron reaching it slightly below its middle height, transversal part (i.e., the part at the level of sternaulus running through the epicnemium to the ventral edge of pronotum) not developed, ventral part (behind fore coxae) slightly elevated. Sternaulus anteriorly impressed. Posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete, slightly elevated. Metanotum ca. $0.4\times$ as long as scutellum. Metapleuron with weak punctures, dorsally weakly sculptured, subpolished, ventrally rugose, juxtacoxal carina basally discernible; submetapleural carina complete, elevated. Pleural carina of propodeum complete; propodeal spiracle elongate oval, separated from pleural carina by less than its length, connected to pleural carina by a distinct ridge. Propodeum short, convex in lateral view, strongly rugose. Propodeal carinae: lateromedian longitudinal carina mostly strong, but behind costula shortly obsolete, at extreme posterior end somewhat weakened; lateral longitudinal carina weak behind costula; anterior transverse carina, including costula, complete and strong; posterior transverse carina only laterally developed. Area basalis triangular, about as long as its anterior width, or shorter and posteriorly merged into a single longitudinal carina. Area superomedia pentagonal, wider than long, its lateral sides behind costulae obsolete, posteriorly opened. Area petiolaris confluent with area superomedia, weakly impressed. Fore wing without areolet, *3rs-m* absent, second recurrent vein (*2m-cu*) postfurcal, intercubitus (*2rs-m*) slightly to distinctly longer than abscissa of *M* between *2rs-m* and *2m-cu*, their angle obtuse; distal abscissa of *Rs* long, straight; nervulus (*cu-a*) postfurcal by about its width, weakly inclivous; postnervulus (abscissa of *Cu1* between *1m-cu* and *Cu1a* + *Cu1b*) intercepted little above its middle by *Cu1a*; lower external angle of second discal cell almost right-angled. Hind wing with nervellus (*cu-a* + abscissa of *Cu1* between *M* and *cu-a*) slightly reclivous, curved, not intercepted by discoidella (*Cu1*); discoidella spectral, proximally not connected to nervellus; axillus vein present. Coxae very finely coriaceous. Hind femur ca. $5.3\text{--}5.5\times$ as long as high, basally narrowed. Inner spur of hind tibia as long as first tarsomere of hind tarsus. Hind basitarsus with a distinct midventral row of closely spaced, short hairs, the row appearing like a sharp carina. Tarsal claws small, about as long as arolium, weakly pectinate.

Metasoma: Metasoma compressed, finely coriaceous to shagreened with weak, barely discernible traces of punctures, and with dense, short hairs. First tergite elongate, $4\times$ as long as its apical width, $1.4\text{--}1.5\times$ as long as second tergite; glymma very small and shallow, indistinct, barely discernible; dorsomedian carina of first tergite absent. First sternite not reaching level of spiracle. Second tergite $2\times$ as long as its apical width; thyridium oval, shallow, its distance from basal margin of tergite subequal to its length. Posterior margins of apical tergites not excised. Claspers apically evenly rounded.

Colour: Flagellum brown, scapus and pedicellus bright yellow with a narrow, brown stripe dorsally. Head black, palpi ivory, mandible yellow, mandibular teeth brown. Mesosoma black, tegula bright yellow. Metasoma pale orange with

a narrow, blackish band on posterior margin of second tergite, last tergite and claspers brown. Wings hyaline, wing veins and pterostigma brown. Fore and middle legs, including coxae, ivory, apical tarsomeres slightly darker. Hind leg, including coxa, pale orange, except tarsus more or less brownish. Hairs with a yellowish, golden tinge, especially on scutellum, metapleuron and propodeum.

Female: Unknown.

Distribution – Australia (Queensland). It is the first species of the genus described from the Australian continent, and from the Australasian region.

Etymology – The specific epithet *chryseus* is the masculine form of the Latinised Greek adjective *chryseus*, *-a*, *-um*, meaning gold-coloured; it refers to the golden pilosity and bright colouration of the new species.

Remarks on identification – The colouration of *Melalophacharops chryseus* sp. nov. is most similar to that of *Melalophacharops persicus* Vas, 2022, recently described from Iran (VAS *et al.* 2022). The latter species can be readily distinguished from the new species by its dark coxae and rather different propodeal carination (lateromedian carina right behind costula well developed, then obsolescent toward apex, showing a reversed pattern of development as compared to the new species, cf. VAS *et al.* (2022: fig. 16)).

The female of the new species is unknown. Except of the presence of a diagnostically short ovipositor (sheath about as long as apical depth of metasoma), females only differ insignificantly from males in other species of *Melalophacharops* where both sexes are known (namely, *Melalophacharops papilionis* (Ashmead, 1905), *Melalophacharops tamanukii* Uchida, 1928, *Melalophacharops everese* (Uchida, 1957)). Therefore, the Diagnosis given above is expected to apply for the hitherto unknown female as well.

Faunistics and biogeography

Campopleginae

Lemophagus curtus Townes, 1965

Material examined – Hungary: Hajdú-Bihar County, Hajdúszoboszló, Ős-Kösely, 10–12.VI.2022, leg. V. Szőke & Z. Vas, Malaise-trap, 2 females.

Remarks – First record for Hungary, collected during the Hungarian Biodiversity Research Society's Biodiversity Days. This species is widely distributed in the Palearctic region, and it was introduced to the USA (YU *et al.* 2016).

Melalophacharops everese (Uchida, 1957)

Material examined – Taiwan: Formosa [= Taiwan], Taihorin [= Dalin], IV.1910, leg. H. Sauter, 1 female and 1 male.

Remarks – First record for Taiwan. This species was described and known from Japan (UCHIDA 1957, YU *et al.* 2016). The specimens from Taiwan are slightly longer (6–7 mm) than the 5 mm body length given by UCHIDA (1957) and KUSIGEMATI (1967) for Japanese specimens; otherwise they are very similar in all taxonomically important character states, therefore their conspecificity is fairly convincing.

Microcharops tibialis (Cresson, 1872)

Material examined – Paraguay: date unknown, leg. Fiebrig, 1 male.

Remarks – First record for Paraguay. This species is widely distributed in the Neotropical and Nearctic regions (YU *et al.* 2016).

Phobocampe confusa (Thomson, 1887)

Material examined – North Macedonia: prov. Skopje, Mts. Karadzica, Sumski Reservat, 2.VI.1998, leg. A. Orosz, one male.

Remarks – First record for North Macedonia. This species is widely distributed in the Western Palaearctic and Nearctic regions (YU *et al.* 2016).

Rhimphoctona megacephalus (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined – Lebanon: Akkar gov., Fnaidek, Quercus forest, 3.VIII.2018, leg. P. Nemes, T. Németh & C. Tannios, reared, emerged from branches at 15.II.2019, 3 females.

Remarks – First record for Lebanon. This species is widely distributed in the Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Hybrizontinae

Ghilaromma fuliginosi (Wilkinson, 1930)

Material examined – Hungary: Pest County, Páty, Mézeshegy, VI.2022, leg. Z. Vas, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for Hungary. This species is widely distributed in the Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016); its occurrence was expected in Hungary (VAS & BAKARDZSIEV 2019).

Mesochorinae

Mesochorus laricis Hartig, 1838

Material examined – Hungary: Bács-Kiskun County, Bugac, 1–10.IX.2018, leg. F. Szentkirályi, light trap, 1 female; same locality, collector and collecting method, 21–31.X.2018, 1 female.

Remarks – First records for Hungary. This species is known from several countries of the Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016, RIEDEL 2018).

Ophioninae

Dicamptus pellucidus (Kriechbaumer, 1894)

Material examined – Kenya: Nairobi, Karen, A Rocha, 1°19'31.54"S, 36°42'8.62"E, 1883m, 24.IX.2022, leg. Sz. Sáfián, 1 male.

Remarks – First record for Kenya. This species is known from several countries of the Afrotropical region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Dictyonotus nigrocyaneus (Tosquinet, 1903)

Material examined – Eritrea: Asmara, date unknown, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for Eritrea. This species is known from a few countries of the Afrotropical region (YU *et al.* 2016); the Eritrean record represents northernmost occurrence of the species in the region.

Enicospilus cederbergi Johansson, 2018

Material examined – Hungary: Hajdú-Bihar County, Hajdúszoboszló, reptér [= airport], 11.VI.2022, leg. V. Szőke & Z. Vas, light trap, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for Hungary, collected during the Hungarian Biodiversity Research Society's Biodiversity Days. This species was recently described from Sweden (JOHANSSON 2018).

Enicospilus exoticus (Morley, 1912)

Material examined – French Guiana: Mt. Kaw, Patawa Camp, 14–31.XII.2019, leg. Sz. Kiss, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for French Guiana. This species is known from several countries of the Neotropical region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus leucocotis (Tosquinet, 1896)

Material examined – Tanzania: D. O. Africa [= German East Africa], Manow, date unknown, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for Tanzania. This species is known from several countries of the Afrotropical region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Enicospilus quietus (Seyrig, 1935)

Material examined – Tanzania: Mawingu Camp, East Usambara, 5°8'37.35"S, 38°35'0.87"E, 988m, 12–14.V.2022, leg. Sz. Sáfián, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for Tanzania. This species is known from some countries of the Afrotropical region (YU *et al.* 2016), and was recently reported from Ghana (VAS 2022).

Ophion areolaris Brauns, 1889

Material examined – Hungary: Bács-Kiskun County, Bugac, 11–20.VI.2018, leg. F. Szentkirályi, light trap, 2 females.

Remarks – First record for Hungary. This species is widely distributed the Western Palaearctic region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Thyreodon atriventris (Cresson, 1874)

Material examined – French Guiana: Mt. Kaw, Patawa Camp, 14–31.XII.2019, leg. Sz. Kiss, 1 female, 1 male; same locality and collector, 21–30.XI.2022, 2 females. Nicaragua: Dpto Granada, Domitila Wildlife Reserve, 11°57.810N, 85°46.377W, tropical dry forest, 9–14.VI.2007, leg. O. Merkl, N. Bálint & T. Németh, at light, 1 female.

Remarks – First records for French Guiana and Nicaragua. This species is widely distributed in the Neotropical region (YU *et al.* 2016).

Thyreodon maculipennis Cresson, 1874

Material examined – Nicaragua: Dpto Granada, Domitila Wildlife Reserve, 11°57.810N, 85°46.377W, tropical dry forest, 9–14.VI.2007, leg. O. Merkl, N. Bálint & T. Németh, at light, 1 female.

Remarks – First record for Nicaragua. This species is known from a few countries of Mesoamerica (YU *et al.* 2016).

*

Acknowledgements – Thanks are due to Juriya Okayasu (Hokkaido University, Sapporo) for taking photos of type specimens deposited in the Hokkaido University, to Viktória Szőke (HNHM) for drawings and post-image works, and to Janko A. Kolarov (University of Plovdiv) for his valuable comments on the manuscript. The author is grateful to Szilárd Kiss and Szabolcs Sáfaián for collecting specimens for the HNHM. This paper was supported by the János Bolyai Research Scholarship of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences.

REFERENCES

- ACHTERBERG C. VAN 1999: The West Palaearctic species of the subfamily Paxylommatinae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae), with special reference to the genus *Hybrizon* Fallén. – *Zoologische Mededelingen Leiden* 73(2): 11–26.
- ASHMEAD W. H. 1905: New Hymenoptera from the Philippine Islands. – *Canadian Entomologist* 37(1): 3–8. <https://doi.org/10.4039/Ent373-1>
- BROCK J. P. 1982: A systematic study of the genus *Ophion* in Britain (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). – *Tijdschrift voor Entomologie* 125(4): 57–97.
- GAULD I. D. & JANZEN D. H. 2004: The systematics and biology of the Costa Rican species of parasitic wasps in the *Thyreodon* genus-group (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 141(3): 297–351. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1096-3642.2004.00116.x>
- GAULD I. D. & MITCHELL P. A. 1978: *The taxonomy, distribution and host preferences of African parasitic wasps of the subfamily Ophioninae*. – CAB, Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, 287 pp.
- GAULD I. D. 1984: *An introduction to the Ichneumonidae of Australia*. – British Museum (Natural History), London, 413 pp.
- GAULD I. D. 1988: A survey of the Ophioninae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) of tropical Mesoamerica with special reference to the fauna of Costa Rica. – *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History), Entomology series* 57: 1–309.
- GAULD I. D. 1991: The Ichneumonidae of Costa Rica, 1. Introduction, keys to subfamilies, and keys to the species of the lower Pimpliform subfamilies Rhyssinae, Poemeniinae, Acaenitinae and Cylloceriinae. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* 47: 1–589.

- GAULD I. D., WAHL D., BRADSHAW K., HANSON P. & WARD S. 1997: The Ichneumonidae of Costa Rica, 2. Introduction and keys to species of the smaller subfamilies, Anomaloninae, Ctenopelmatinae, Diplazontinae, Lycorininae, Phrudinae, Tryphoninae (excluding Netelia) and Xoridinae, with an appendix on the Rhyssinae. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* 57: 1–485.
- GUPTA V. K. 1987: A revision of the genus *Microcharops* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Contributions to the American Entomological Institute* 23(2): 1–42.
- HORSTMANN K. 1980: Revision der europäischen Arten der Gattung *Rhimphoctona* Förster (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). – *Nachrichtenblatt der Bayerischen Entomologen* 29: 17–24.
- HORSTMANN K. 2004: Bemerkungen zur Systematik einiger Gattungen der Campopleginae IV (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae). – *Zeitschrift der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Österreichischer Entomologen* 56: 13–35.
- JOHANSSON N. 2018: Review of the Swedish *Enicospilus* (Hymenoptera; Ichneumonidae; Ophioninae) with description of three new species and an illustrated key to species. – *European Journal of Taxonomy* 483: 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.5852/ejt.2018.483>
- KASPARYAN D. R. 1976: (The new species of Ichneumonids of the subfamily Campopleginae (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) from the Eastern Palearctic.) – *Trudy Zoologicheskogo Instituta* 64: 68–75.
- KUSIGEMATI K. 1967: New host records of Ichneumonidae from Japan. – *Insecta Matsumurana* 29: 50.
- KUSIGEMATI K. 1987: Porizontinae and Diplazontinae collected by the Hokkaido University Expedition to Nepal Himalaya, 1968 (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Memoirs of the Kagoshima University, Research Center for the South Pacific* 8(1): 34–51.
- RIEDEL M. 2018: Contribution to the Palearctic species of *Mesochorus* Gravenhorst (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Mesochorinae): 1. The *M. fulvus*-group. – *Linzer biologische Beiträge* 50(1): 687–716. <https://doi.org/10.21248/contrib.entomol.68.1.1-29>
- SEDIVY J. 2004: European species of the genus *Phobocampe* Förster (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Acta Universitatis Carolinae Biologica* 48: 203–235.
- SONAN J. 1930: A few host known Ichneumonidae found in Japan and Formosa. – *Transactions of the Natural History Society of Formosa* 20: 268–273.
- TOWNES H. 1969: The genera of Ichneumonidae. Part 1. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* 11: 1–300.
- TOWNES H. 1970: The genera of Ichneumonidae. Part 3. – *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* 13: 1–307.
- UCHIDA T. 1928: Zweiter Beitrag zur Ichneumoniden-Fauna Japans. – *Journal of the Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University* 21: 177–297.
- UCHIDA T. 1932: H. Sauter's Formosa-Ausbeute. Ichneumonidae (Hym.). – *Journal of the Faculty of Agriculture, Hokkaido University* 33: 133–222.
- UCHIDA T. 1957: Drei aus den Schmetterlingslarven gezuechtete Ichneumonidenarten. – *Insecta Matsumurana* 21: 59–61.

- VARGA O. 2017: A review of the genus *Rhimphoctona* Förster, 1869 (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae) from the Ukrainian Carpathians, with a key to European species. – *Zootaxa* **4263**(2): 387–394. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4263.2.12>
- VAS Z. & BAKARDZSIEV K. 2019: Hybrizontinae of Hungary (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **80**: 273–278. <https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2019.80.273>
- VAS Z. 2022: New species and new records of ichneumon wasps from Africa (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Campopleginae, Cryptinae, Ophioninae). – *Folia entomologica hungarica* **83**: 25–39. <https://doi.org/10.17112/FoliaEntHung.2022.83.25>
- VAS Z., REZAEI SH., FALLAHZADEH M., MOHAMMADI-KHORAMABADI A., SAGHAEI N. & LJUBOMIROV T. 2022: Contributions to the taxonomy, identification, and biogeography of Palaearctic Campopleginae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae), with the descriptions of four new species from Iran. – *Zootaxa* **5134**(2): 261–274. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5134.2.5>
- YU D. S. & HORSTMANN K. 1997: *A catalogue of world Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera)*. – The American Entomological Institute, Gainesville, 1558 pp.
- YU D. S., VAN ACHTERBERG C. & HORSTMANN K. 2016: *Taxapad 2016, Ichneumonoidea 2015*. – Database on flash-drive. www.taxapad.com, Nepean, Ontario, Canada.